

EDUCATIONAL CONCEPTUAL ISSUES IN PERSON-ORIENTED PEDAGOGY

Rakhimov Aktam Husenovich

Associate Professor of the department of "Physics and Electronics"

Karshi Engineering Economics institute

ABSTRACT

The article describes the content and essence of person-oriented education, the main factors of humanistic pedagogy, self-activation and evaluation criteria, the interaction between teachers and students and students in the field of humanistic pedagogy. The main characteristics of individuals with the ability of self-activation and the necessary conditions for the implementation of self-assessment and self-activation methods of students are based.

Key words and phrases: *humanistic pedagogy, person-centered education, self-activation, self-evaluation, criterion, factor, condition.*

КИРИШ

Implementation of the reforms carried out in the way of radical change of the education system in our republic and creation of comprehensive conditions for a deep understanding of the nature of the documents adopted in this regard by the general public are the most urgent tasks of the state administration, law enforcement agencies, and employees of educational institutions. Humanity has progressed only because of independent learning [1]. Therefore, educational technologies should mainly focus on the formation of competencies such as self-development, activation and improvement, self-assessment in students. Currently, in the educational system of developed countries, great attention is paid to such educational and pedagogical technologies [2]. Such modern innovative technologies include developmental educational technology,

technology of step-by-step formation of mental movement, collective interaction technology, full mastery technology, multi-level teaching technology, adaptive teaching technology, programmed teaching technology, problem-based teaching technology, modular teaching technology, technology of development of creative activities of future specialists, project style technologies [3].

The application of such pedagogical technologies is one of the important conditions for correctly assessing the knowledge, learning and skills of students in the existing educational environment, clearly determining the level of formation of professional competence in them and accordingly recommending them to work in production enterprises, ensuring the competitiveness of trained personnel [4].

RESEARCH METHODS

In the research process, the analysis of scientific and teaching-methodical literature, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment-test and foresight methods were used.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In person-oriented education, which is considered one of the central concepts of humanitarian (humanitarian) pedagogy, self-activation or awakening of all one's potential abilities and natural talent and applying it in life, self-activation, self-confidence play an important role. Of course, a person's happiness and peace of mind are formed in constant dependence on these qualities of a person. This is also evaluated by factors such as the correct assessment of a person's own capabilities, the creation of self-confidence characteristics [5]. In psychology, the concept of "waiting" is sometimes found. For example, if a teacher shows in all his relations and actions that he does not expect any positive results from a certain student in his subject, this student will also believe it. This means that the student is in a "waiting" state, because the student is already doomed to failure. Also, on the contrary, if the teacher believes even the most backward student and convinces him that he can master the subject, he just

needs to make a little effort, even little by little positive mastering will occur in the student. [6].

A.A. Leontev shows the following signs of unknowingly negative attitude towards the student in the teacher's activity:

➤ the teacher allocates less time for the answer to the "bad" student than to the good student, that is, he does not create an opportunity to think;

➤ if a "bad" student gives an incorrect answer, he does not repeat the question in a broader way, does not help him to answer the question, suddenly asks another student or gives the correct answer himself, that is, he does not create conditions for the student to think and develop his own opinion;

➤ the teacher sometimes behaves "liberally" and positively evaluates the wrong answer of a good student; кўпгина ҳолатларда «ёмон» талабани нотўғри жавоби учун уришади;

➤ even when he answers correctly, he rarely praises or encourages;

➤ he does not trust the "bad" student to answer, he does not ask him, even when he raises his hand for an answer, he does not pay attention;

➤ a bad student looks less in the eyes than a good student, shows less affection towards him;

➤ does little or no independent work during training.

In the person-oriented field of humanistic pedagogy, special attention is paid to the relationship between the teacher and the student and the students. The student should trust the teacher and know the teacher not as a person who conveys knowledge, but as a kind, demanding, open-minded teacher [7].

K. Rodgers explains the main factors of humanistic pedagogy as follows:

✓ the teacher accepts the idea that all students have the ability to read;

✓ curriculum meets student interests;

✓ creation of a free environment in the audience, no pressure from the teacher;

✓ creation of opportunities for students to actively participate in the activities of the educational institution;

- ✓ self-assessment (except for external assessment);
- ✓ not only the result of the learning process, but also the constant openness of participation and responsibility.

The center of the concept of person-oriented education is self-activation and it is aimed at developing the internal resources of a person [8]. A. Maslov defines the main characteristics of individuals with the ability to self-activate as follows:

- accepts reality clearly, without hesitation;
- quickly and accurately perceives himself and others;
- is highly independent;
- has high accuracy and focus in solving problems;
- extreme indifference and tends to be alone;
- resists independently and culturally;
- rich in emotional reactions;
- has a good relationship with others;
- is highly satisfied with his situation;
- democratic character;
- has a strong creative ability;
- has high human qualities;
- has a high frequency of high-intensity experiences.

It is interesting to work with such individuals and they can find their place in life without making great demands and complaints to parents, teachers and the state. They are independent, self-directed individuals depending on their abilities. It is not easy to educate such students. However, a teacher working on the principle of humanistic pedagogy, person-oriented education should be able to find a way to the heart of such a student [9]. The following conditions should be created in the educational institution for the implementation of self-assessment and self-activation methods of students within the framework of humanistic pedagogy [10,11]:

- ✓ open and flexible class schedule;
- ✓ paying great attention to the independent activity of students;
- ✓ creating ample opportunities for students to learn independently;
- ✓ attach serious importance to creative works of students;
- ✓ pay attention to mutual support in the educational process;
- ✓ special attention to self-assessment;
- ✓ respecting students' personal worth and abilities.

Working in small groups is carried out on the basis of mutual support and joint activity. In this case, the issues of self-esteem and respect for the dignity of a person are very sensitive.

CONCLUSIONS

It is difficult to understand the didactic significance of innovative pedagogical technologies being studied and to determine its place in the educational system without clearly imagining the essence of self-evaluation in becoming a person and a specialist. Self-activation or awakening of all one's potential abilities and natural talent and applying it in life, self-activation, self-confidence play an important role in person-oriented education. In the person-oriented field of humanistic pedagogy, it is necessary to pay special attention to the relationship between the teacher and the student and the students. The teacher's relationship with the student should be sincere and natural, and there should be no artificiality in meeting the student's needs and answering his questions. If the demand is higher than the opportunity, it will be difficult to achieve success or not at all, which will also damage one's reputation and health. Also, the smallness of demand prevents a person from self-activation and creativity. The student should trust the teacher, know the teacher not as a person who conveys knowledge, but as a kind, demanding, open-minded teacher.

REFERENCES

1. Rakhimov O. D., Manzarov Yu. Kh., Ashurova L. Initial foresight studies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan // Modern education (Uzbekistan). – 2021. – №. 4 (101). – P. 16-22.
2. Clarin M.V. Innovations in global pedagogy. Riga, 1995.
3. Polat E.S., New pedagogical and information technologies in education systems units. E.S. Polat - M., 2004
4. Rakhimov O. D., Chorshanbiev Z. E. Prospects for the application of digital technologies in training the "labor protection" course //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – 2021. – T. 2. – P. 34-40.
5. Rakhimov O. et al. Positive and negative aspects of digitalization of higher education in Uzbekistan //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing, 2022. – T. 2432. – №. 1.
6. Dustkabilovich R. O. et al. Foresight as an Innovative Technology for Researching the Future Development of Universities in Uzbekistan: First Steps towards Foresight //Psychology and Education Journal. – 2021. – T. 58. – №. 5. – P. 1838-1847.
7. New values of education. Vol. #6: Caring - Support - Counseling. / M.: Innovator, 1996. - 196 p.
8. Rakhimov O. D. et al. Unused opportunities: distance education in Uzbekistan //Scientific journal. – 2021. – №. 3. – P. 58.
9. Rakhimov O. D., Chorshanbiev Z. E., Rakhimov A. X. Organization of distance education in the higher education system of Uzbekistan. Monograph //Karshi, "Intellect" publishing house. - 2021.
10. Novikov A.M. Methodology of education. / M.: Egves, 2002. - 320 p.
11. Doniyorova G.Sh Teaching English for specific purposes for financial students: methods and analysis.// Science and Education. Volume 4, issue 6. – 2023. Pages 736-739.